

A CASE REPORT ON THE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS
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ABSTRACT

Prameha in *Ayurveda* can be correlated with Diabetes Mellitus (DM). DM is a metabolic disorder characterized by high blood glucose level & associated with other manifestations. ‘Diabetes’ means ‘polyuria’ and ‘mellitus’ means ‘honey’. In *Ayurveda*, it is a *tridosha vyadhi* but mainly *Kapha Pradhan & meda, mansa, kleda, rakta, vasa, majja, lasika, shukra, rasa & ojas* are the *dushyas*. Here is a single case study demonstrating the role of *Ayurveda* in management of DM type I. A 39 years old Indian male came for consultation in OPD of SMBT Ayurved Hospital with complaints of *Hrudrava, Svedaadhikya, Bharashaya, Dourbalya, Pindikaudvesthan, Bahumutrata, Adhmana* since last 6 months; for which various combination of herbal formulations was given. Good result was observed on reducing the above symptoms by the treatment regimen; insulin dose was reduced from 10 units ----8 units to now only to 5 units before lunch & HbA1c level was 10.5% (3/7/2024), which was reduced by 9.5% (12/12/2024) after 5 months of treatment.

KEYWORDS: *Prameha*, Diabetes Mellitus Type I, HbA1c, Insulin, *Ayurveda*.**INTRODUCTION**

DM is a group of metabolic diseases which is presented with high blood glucose level resulting from defects in production of insulin or their action or both. It may lead to serious health complications in multiple organs. Diabetes is of two types - type I, also known as Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM) and type II, which is also known as Non - Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM). When there is complete or near total insulin deficiency, it is termed as type I while in type II it is characterized by resistance or impaired insulin secretion and increased glucose production.^[1] The classical symptoms of diabetes mellitus are polyuria (frequent urination), polydipsia (increased thirst) and polyphagia (increased hunger). The prevalence rate of DM type I is 11.6 % in India.^[2] It is increasing globally with a rise from about 30 million cases in 1985 to 177 million cases in 2000 and worldwide estimates project

that more than 360 million individuals will have diabetes by the year 2030.^[3]

In today's era, the occurrence of diseases has been increased due to an unhealthy lifestyle, and *Ayurveda* is being helped in a very good manner for this disease treatment. *Prameha* is seen as one of the commonest lifestyle diseases among the people. Various, *Acharyas* have described *Prameha* such as *Charka*^[4,5], *Sushruta*^[6], *Vagbhat*^[7], etc. *Prameha* has been classified into 20 types, in the predominance of *Tridosha* such as *Vaat Pitta & Kapha, Dushya*, such as *Meda, Mansa, Kleda, Rakta, Vasa, Majja, Lasika, Shukra, Rasa & Ojas*.^[8] The *Ayurvedic* management of *Prameha* includes dietary lifestyle recommendations & herbs & herbal formulations according to the various pathophysiological conditions. Here is a single case study in which the role of *Ayurveda* in the management of DM type I is demonstrated.

Presenting complaints

A 39 – year - old Indian male came for consultation in Out Patient Department of SMBT Ayurved Hospital for complaints of *Hrudrava*, *Svedaadhikya*, *Bharashaya*, *Dourbalya*, *Pindikaudvesthan*, *Bahumutrata*, *Adhmana* since last 6 months. He was having history of DM type I since last 17 years for which daily he administrated 18 units of insulin. No history of hypertension or any other major illness noted. Presently, he came to SMBT Ayurved Hospital for further treatment of *Prameha*.

Clinical Findings

On examination of the patient, the pulse was 74/min and blood pressure were 140/90 mm Hg. He had *tikshna agni*, *mrudu kostha*, tongue was coated. Patient was

having *vaatkaphaj prakriti* with *madhyam sara*, *madhyam shamhan*, *madhyam praman*, *madhyam satyma*, *hina satva*, *madhyam ahara shakti* & *Jaran Shakti*, *medovaha*, *mutravaha*, *svedavaha strotastodushti*. His HbA1c level was 10.5% (3/7/2024).

Treatment & Outcome

- Patient was administered with various ayurvedic drug formulations which are mentioned below in the treatment regimen table.
- There after the patient is living well & living normal health & continuing his life with reduction of insulin dose to 5 units before lunch.

DATE	CLINICAL FINDINGS	TREATMENT
7/8/2024	<p>c/o –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hrudrava</i> (palpitations) ++ - <i>Svedaadhikya</i> (sweating) ++ - <i>Bharashaya</i> (weight loss) ++ - <i>Dourbalya</i> (weakness) ++ - <i>Pindikaudvesthan</i> ++ - <i>Bahumutrata</i> ++ - <i>Adhmana</i> ++ <p>o/e –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bp – 140/ 90 mm Hg - P – 74/ min <p>Weight – 46 kg</p>	<p>Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each</p> <hr/> <p>1spoon -----0 -----1 spoon before meal with warm water. Chandrabhavati 1 -----0 -----1 after meal with warm water. Dashmool kwatha 4 tsp -----0-----4tsp before meal with warm water</p> <p>Duration - For 15 days. HbA1c – 10.5 (3/7/2024) Insulin dose – 10 units -----8 units</p>
20/8/2024	<p>c/o –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hrudrava</i> (palpitations) + - <i>Svedaadhikya</i> (sweating) + - <i>Bharashaya</i> (weight loss) + - <i>Dourbalya</i> (weakness) + - <i>Pindikaudvesthan</i> + - <i>Bahumutrata</i> ++ - <i>Adhmana</i> ++ - <i>Prusthashool</i> + <p>o/e –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bp – 120/70 mm Hg - P – 78/min <p>Weight – 46 kg</p>	<p>Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each</p> <hr/> <p>1 spoon -----0 -----1 spoon before meal with warm water.</p> <p>Chandrabhavati 1 -----0 -----1 after meal with warm water. Dashmool kwatha 4 tsp -----0-----4tsp before meal with warm water Lavanbhaskar churna 3 gm each Yashtimadhu churna 1 gm each</p> <hr/> <p>0 -----0 -----1 at night with kosha jaal Duration – For 7 days 19/8/2024 – BSL F – 170mg/dl BSL PP – 230 mg/dl Insulin dose – decreased – 8 units -----5 units</p>

<p>31/8/2024</p>	<p>c/o –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hrudrava</i> (palpitations) + - <i>Svedaadhikya</i> (sweating) + - <i>Bharashaya</i> (weight loss) - <i>Dourbalya</i> (weakness) + - <i>Pindikaudvesthan</i> - <i>Bahumutrata</i> + - <i>Adhmana</i> + - <i>Prusthashool</i> <p>↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓</p> <p>o/e –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bp – 160/90 mmhg - P – 70 mm Hg <p>Weight – 47.2 kg</p>	<p>Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each</p> <hr/> <p>1 spoon -----0 -----1 spoon before meal with warm water.</p> <p>Chandrabhavati 1 -----0 -----1 after meal with warm water.</p> <p>Dashmool kwatha 4 tsp -----0-----4tsp before meal with warm water</p> <p>Lavanbhaskar churna 3gm each Yashtimadhu churna 1 gm each</p> <hr/> <p>1-----0 -----1 at night with kosha jaal</p> <p>Sthanik snehan svedan – katipradeshi Sahcharadhi tail for local application</p> <p>Duration - For 7 days Insulin dose - 8 units -----5 units</p>
<p>13/9/2024</p>	<p>c/o –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hrudrava</i> (palpitations) - <i>Svedaadhikya</i> (sweating) - <i>Bharashaya</i> (weight loss) - <i>Dourbalya</i> (weakness) - <i>Pindikaudvesthan</i> - <i>Bahumutrata</i> + - <i>Adhmana</i> - <i>Prusthashool</i> <p>↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓</p> <p>o/e –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bp – 180/100 mm Hg - P – 84/ min <p>Weight – 47.4 kg</p>	<p>Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each</p> <hr/> <p>1 spoon -----0 ----1 spoon before meal with warm water.</p> <p>Chandrabhavati 1 -----0 -----1 after meal with warm water.</p> <p>Dashmool kwatha 4 tsp -----0-----4tsp before meal with warm water</p> <p>Sitopaladi churna – 2 gm each Hingavastak churna each 3 gm Shankhabhasma – 500 mg</p> <hr/> <p>1tsp -----0 -----1 tsp after meal with goghrita.</p> <p>Duration – For 15 days Insulin dose - 8 units -----5 units</p>
<p>25/9/2024</p>	<p>c/o –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Dourbalya</i> - <i>Adhmaan</i> - <i>Prustashool</i> - <i>Bahumutrata</i> <p>↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓</p> <p>o/e –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bp – 150/80 mm Hg - P – 72/ min <p>Weight – 47.1 kg</p>	<p>Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each</p> <hr/> <p>1 spoon -----0 ----1 spoon before meal with warm water.</p> <p>Chandrabhavati 1 -----0 -----1 after meal with warm water.</p> <p>Dashmool kwatha 4 tsp -----0-----4tsp before meal with warm water</p> <p>Sitopaladi churna – 2 gm each Hingavastak churna each 3 gm Shankhabhasma – 500 mg</p>

		1tsp -----0 -----1 tsp after meal with goghrita. Duration – For 15 days Insulin dose - 8 units -----5 units
18/10/2024	c/o – - <i>Dourbalya</i> ↓ - <i>Udarshool</i> ++ in the last 2 days o/e – - Bp – 150/80 mm Hg - P – 83/min Weight – 46.6 Kgs	Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each ----- Ispoon -----0 -----1 spoon before meal with warm water. Gokshuradi guggul -----0-----2 after meal with koszna jaal Lavan Bhaskar churna 3 gm Yashtimadhu 1 gm each 0 -----0 -----1 at night with warm water. Duration – For 15 days. Insulin dose - 8 units -----5 units
15/11/2024	c/o – - <i>Dourbalya</i> ↓ - <i>Adhmaan</i> ↓ o/e – - Bp – 130/80 mmhg ↓ - P – 72/ min Weight – 46.3 kgs	Amalki – 2gm each Daruharidra 500 mg each ----- 1 -----0-----1 with madhu/warm water in rasayan kaal Triphala – each 2 gm Daruhardidra – each 1 gm Ashwagandha – each 1 gm Shunti – 500 mg each ----- Ispoon -----0 -----1 spoon before meal with warm water. Gokshuradi guggul 2-----0-----2 after meal with koszna jaal Lavan Bhaskar churna 3 gm Yashtimadhu 1 gm each ----- 0 -----0 -----1 at night with warm water Duration – For 15 days Insulin dose – Decreased to – 7 units -----5 units.
4/12/2024	c/o – - <i>shirashool</i> since yesterday o/e – - Bp – 150/90 mm Hg - P – 87/min Weight – 47.03 Kg	Jatamansi – 2 gm each Brahmi – 2gm each Shankha Bhasma – 500 mg ----- 0 -----0-----1 phantavidhi Duration – For 7 days Insulin dose – 7 units -----5 units
13/12/2024	c/o – - <i>Shirashool</i> ↓ o/e – - Bp – 140/80 mm Hg - P – 82/min Weight – 46.95 Kg	Daruharidra 1 gm each Guduchi 1 gm each Amalki 1 gm each Gokshur 1 gm each Shankhabhasma 500 mg ----- 1 -----0-----1 after meal with warm water. Jatamansi – 2 gm each

	<p>Brahmi – 2gm each Shankha Bhasma – 500 mg</p> <hr/> <p>0 -----0-----1 phantavidhi</p> <p>Lavanbhaskar 3gm each Yastimadhu 1gm each</p> <hr/> <p>0 -----0 -----1 at night with warm water</p> <p>Gokshuradhi guggul 2-----0-----2 after meal with warm water.</p> <p>Duration – For 15 days. Insulin dose – Decreased to → 5 Units before lunch HbA1c – 9.5 (12/12/2024)</p>
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Follow – up

- Good result was observed on reducing the *Hrudrava, Svedaadhikya, Bharashaya, Dourbalya, Pindikaudvesthan, Bahumutrata, Adhmana* by the treatment regimen.
- Hematological parameter was reinvestigated on 3/7/2024 at this time HbA1c level was 10.5% which was reduced to 9.5% on 12/12/2024 after 5 months of treatment.

Test	Bt	At (5 month)
HbA1c	10.5%	9.5%

DISSCUSSION

A patient with high dose of insulin being administrated daily 18 units has been treated with *Ayurvedic* treatment as described above. To start with various *ayurvedic* drug formulations were being administrated. This has resulted in achieving in reducing the insulin dose, HbA1c level and improved quality of life as indicated in major *ayurveda* parameters. There after the patient is living well & living normal health & continuing his life with reduction of insulin dose to 5 units before lunch.

Drug action

Sr.No.	Drug	Mode of Action
1.	<i>Triphala Churna</i>	By inhibiting the digestive enzymes and may decrease absorption of glucose through inhibition of glycolytic enzymes, thereby reducing blood glucose levels.
2.	<i>Daruharidra churna</i>	The berberine stimulates glycolysis by increasing the activity of glucokinases, improving insulin secretion, and inhibiting gluconeogenesis and adipogenesis in the liver. Insulin sensitivity is enhanced by the activation of 5-adenosine monophosphate kinase (AMPK).
3.	<i>Ashwagandha churna</i>	It helps in balancing the endocrine function.
4.	<i>Shunti churna</i>	It activates the digestive enzymes, improving blood circulation, and potentially acting as an antioxidant due to its bioactive compounds like gingerols and shogaols.
5.	<i>Chandraprabhavati</i>	It acts as an anti – hyperglycemic agent, meaning it helps lower blood sugar levels by potentially improving insulin sensitivity, reducing glucose absorption from the gut, and regulating lipid profiles, thereby aiding in the management of diabetes complications associated with high blood sugar and cholesterol levels.
6.	<i>Dashmool Kwatha</i>	It acts on the Vata Dosha by reducing its aggravation.
7.	<i>Lavanbhaskar Churna</i>	It is effective in reducing flatulence, intestinal gas, bloating, and abdominal heaviness due to the presence of bioactive substances such as sea and rock salt, cumin, coriander, jeera, and laung.
8.	<i>Yashtimadhu Churna</i>	its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and demulcent properties, which help soothe irritated tissues, protect the mucous membranes, and promote healing
9.	<i>Sitopaladi Churna</i>	It helps remove dryness and release sputum out of the respiratory tract.
10.	Hingasvastak Churna	Deepan (appetizer) and Pachan (digestion)
11.	Shankhabhasma	It pacifies the irregularities related to Kapha and Vata but in addition it also acts as a natural alkalizer which counteracts the hydrochloric acid secretion and eases acidity.
12.	Gokshuradhi Guggul	<i>Anulomak</i> , it increases urine production and thus provides relief from painful urination due to its <i>Tridosha (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha)</i> balancing and <i>Mutral</i> (diuretic) properties.

CONCLUSION

Prameha can be correlated to Diabetes Mellitus in Modern Science. The *Ayurvedic* line of treatment mentioned in the classics were fruitful in the treatment of the patient. In *Krishna Pramehi* which includes conditions such as, DM type 1 or Juvenile DM and long-standing cases of uncontrolled blood sugars with severe weight loss should be administered with *Brimhana* (nourishing) line of treatment as mentioned in classics. The combine effects of above herbo – minerals drugs were useful in treating pathology of *Prameha* and reducing the insulin dose of the patient. It is clearly indicated by these observations that how a patient of DM type1 and receiving insulin, can get rid of insulin. This kind of approach may be taken into consideration for further treatment & research work of *Prameha*.

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